

A Study of the Interaction between Thionyl Chloride and Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene (-CH₂-) Group. Part IV.

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A close study of the reactions of thionyl chloride with organic compounds clearly shows that the course of reaction followed by thionyl chloride is entirely guided by the conditions of experiment in many cases. The reaction of thionyl chloride with phenols, phenetoles and alcohols might be cited as examples of this type. Generally in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, these compounds give rise to sulphides. But by slightly changing the conditions of the experiment, the same reaction can be made to follow a different course, as a result of which sulphoxides are obtained (Loth and Michaelis, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2540; Smiles and Rossignol, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 98, 745). Hence it was thought interesting to examine the course of the reaction followed by thionyl chloride when it reacts with substances containing a reactive methylene (-CH₂-) group in cold ethereal solution, although a similar reaction in boiling benzene solution had already resulted in the formation of sulphoxides (Naik, Desai and Parekh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 137; Naik and Thosar, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 127); and as will be seen from the experiments recorded in this paper this expectation is completely fulfilled.

Thionyl chloride was made to react with the following amides in presence of cold anhydrous ether.

(1) Acetoacetanilide, (2) acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, (3) acetoacet-*m*-toluidide, (4) acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, (5) acetoacet- β -naphthylamide, (6) acetoacet-1:3:4-xylidide, (7) malondi-*n*-propylamide, (8) malondi-isobutylamide, (9) malondiamylamide, (10) malondiheptylamide, (11) ethylmalon-*o*-tolylamate, (12) ethylmalon-*p*-tolylamate, (13) ethylmalon- β -naphthylamate, (14) ethylmalon-1:3:4-xylilamate, (15) ethylmalon-1:4:5-xylilamate.

The amides slowly went into solution, from which sulphides began to separate out, the reaction being complete after several days, the

time required depending upon the nature of the amide used. Amides (1) to (10) gave sulphides of the general constitution,

(where R=phenyl, tolyl, naphthyl, xylil or propyl groups and R' is either a CH₃ or -NHR group); but in the case of amides (9) and (10) the reaction products were liquids which did not solidify even when placed in a freezing mixture. They will be worked up later. On the other hand the amates (11) to (15) gave sulphides of the formula

The above constitution of these sulphides follows from the following considerations:

(i) That the two hydrogen atoms are not supplied by the phenyl group, since (a) acetoacetic ester, which does not contain such a phenyl group reacts with thionyl chloride in a similar manner (Michaelis and Philips, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 559); (b) malondi-*n*-propylamide containing no phenyl nucleus also reacts with thionyl chloride to give a similar compound.

(ii) That the hydrogen atoms eliminated are not those, which are originally attached to the nitrogen atom of -NHR group, for (a) ethyl acetoacetate which does not contain such a hydrogen atom reacts similarly with thionyl chloride; (b) in case of malondi-*n*-propylamide which contains two such amido hydrogen atoms only one is replaced. On the supposition that the hydrogen atom of the -NHR group is reactive both these hydrogen atoms must react.

Finally in order to establish that these compounds are not sulphoxides of the formula

advantage was taken of the fact that Michaelis and Philips had actually obtained a sulphide of acetoacetic ester by the action of thionyl chloride upon it (*loc. cit.*). As the conditions used by these authors were slightly different from those used here, thionyl chloride

was made to react with acetoacetic ester under exactly the same conditions as were used here and it was found that the product obtained was identical with that obtained by the above authors. This sulphide of acetoacetic ester has been prepared by a host of workers from various sources so as to leave no doubt as to its constitution (Buehka, *Ber.*, 1885, **18**, 2092; Delisle, *ibid.*, 1889, **22**, 306; Schönbrodt, *Annalen*, 1889, **253**, 198; Sprague, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, **59**, 329).

The reaction of thionyl chloride with amates (11) to (15) is also in favour of the sulphide constitution for the following reasons:

(i) These amates, when they were made to react with thionyl chloride in *boiling benzene*, where there is a greater possibility of the formation of sulphoxides, gave rise to liquid products (Naik, Desai and Parekh, *loc. cit.*).

(ii) The reaction products obtained here are white crystalline substances, whereas the sulphoxides of the linking :C:S:O obtained till now are always coloured substances.

Michaelis and Philips (*loc. cit.*) hold that in such reactions, thionyl chloride behaves as if it were a mixture of sulphur dichloride and sulphuryl chloride, $2 \text{SOCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{SCl}_2, \text{SO}_2\text{Cl}_2$, sulphur dichloride reacting with acetoacetic ester with the formation of the above sulphide. This view is further confirmed by the reaction of thionyl chloride with aromatic tertiary amines yielding two different products as represented by the equations:

the second product being obtained by the action of sulphuryl chloride (SO_2Cl_2) on the amine (Michaelis and Godchaux, *Ber.*, 1890, **25**, 553). The reaction of thionyl chloride with phenol also gives a sulphide together with other substances containing both sulphur and chlorine (Tassinari, *Gazzetta*, 1890, **20**, 362).

The same explanation can very well be given in the reaction studied here.

The course of the reaction followed by SO_2Cl_2 cannot be definitely ascertained here, as the mother liquor on evaporation gives only a semi solid mass, which it is proposed to work up later. In all probability the course followed by the reaction is different from that followed under ordinary conditions where chloro compounds are obtained (Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 11). It is just possible that the catalytic action of thionyl chloride might again play its important part here and give rise to compounds of the type obtained in the case of tertiary amines and phenols.

The reaction in the case of amates (11) to (15) can be represented as

Such a course of reaction is not an abnormal one. Many instances can be cited where under similar conditions both the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group of the amates react, whereas usually only one hydrogen atom of the methylene group in the case of the aliphatic amides of malonic acid is found to react (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 379; West, *ibid.*, 1922, **121**, 2196; Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 111; Naik and Shah, *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 11; Norris and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1208). The course of reaction where only one hydrogen atom takes part, is explained by supposing that the second hydrogen atom becomes sluggish after the first is replaced by a substituent.

From the consideration of the time taken to complete the reaction (*vide* experimental) in a series such as,

(I)

(II)

(III)

the time required for the completion of the reaction in the case of the type (III) is longer than that required in the case of type (II), which in its own turn was found to be less reactive than type (I). This is quite in accord with the hypothesis put forward by Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1166), and supported by the experimental work carried on in these laboratories since then. That the com.

pounds of type (II) are less reactive than those of type (I) follows from the fact that the total negativity of the adjoining carbonyl groups in type (II) is made smaller than that in type (I), by the replacement of a carbethoxy group in place of acetyl group, the other (-CONHR) group being common to all the three types. This total negativity is still further reduced in compounds of the type (III) where both the carbonyl groups are partially neutralised by the -NHR group and hence in this case the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group is the least and the time required for the completion of the reaction longest.

On examining the properties of these compounds it was found that the thio grouping (-S-) in these compounds is not so stable as the dithio grouping in the compounds obtained by Naik by the action of sulphur monochloride on substances containing the reactive methylene group (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1166, 1231). Thus, while the dithio grouping is quite unaffected by fuming nitric acid and silver nitrate, the thio grouping in these compounds is destroyed, giving rise to free sulphuric acid in the first case, and silver sulphide in the other. The sulphides derived from amates are still more unstable and are gradually decomposed on keeping for a long time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiobisacetoacetanilide.—Thionyl chloride (2.5 g.) was added to pure dry acetoacetanilide (3.5 g.) suspended in dry ether (30 c. c.) in a conical flask tightly corked with a calcium chloride tube to avoid moisture and left at room temperature (28-30°). The amide slowly went in solution (3 hours) and the ethereal solution attained a rich red colour. On the next day white hexagonal plates began to separate out. After 3 days, when the reaction was complete the separated solid was filtered at the pump and washed with dry ether to free it from the excess of thionyl chloride. After crystallising it from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum (b. p. 50-60°) the substance was obtained in the form of white, hard, prismatic needles, m. p. 132°. But this substance was found to contain traces of hydrochloric acid from which, it could not be freed even on repeated crystallisations or keeping it in an alkali desiccator for a long time. The melting point also remained unchanged. Hence the substance was dissolved in benzene and boiled with a small amount of animal charcoal (0.2 g.)

under reflux for nearly 6 hours. The clear filtrate from animal charcoal was allowed to cool after adding an equal amount of dry light petroleum. The resulting product was now free from hydrochloric acid and was obtained in the form of white silky needles, m. p. 147° . It is interesting to note here that the impure compound had the same melting point (132°) in whatever conditions it was taken out of the reaction mixture. The analysis of the impure substance also amounted to nearly 1 mol. of hydrochloric acid in combination with 1 mol. of the sulphide.

The substance is readily soluble in benzene, sparingly so in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide and insoluble in petroleum ether and ether. (Found: N, 7.35; S, 7.90. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.29; S, 8.33 per cent.).

All other sulphides were similarly prepared by treating the respective amides with thionyl chloride under the above conditions. A slight excess of thionyl chloride than required by equation was always necessary to compensate for the loss caused by gradual decomposition. All the sulphides except those obtained from amides had to be purified by boiling with animal charcoal for 6 hours. The results of these experiments are tabulated in Table I.

Hydrolysis of thiobisacetoacet- β -naphthylamide.—The compound (3 g.) was added to the solution of caustic potash (7 g.) in water (8 c. c.) and refluxed for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled and filtered. It was washed with cold water till it was free from alkali. The solid was crystallised from hot water, when characteristic rosy leaflets separated out, m. p. 111° . The substance was identified as β -naphthylamine and confirmed by mixed melting point. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the solid obtained was treated with hydrochloric acid when H_2S was found to evolve.

TABLE I.
 [T = Thiobisacetate ; D = Thiobismalon ; E = Ethylmalon]

Name	Formula.	Appearance.	M. p.	Duration of reaction. (days)	Analysis Found.	Analysis Calc.
T-acetanilide	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2S$	Silky needles	147°	3	S, 7.90 N, 7.3	8.9 p. c. 7.29
T-o-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2S$	Light flakes	160°	3	S, 7.6	7.76
T-m-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2S$	Prismatic needles	104°	3	N, 6.6 S, 7.53	6.79 7.76
T-p-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2S$	Silky needles	174°	3	S, 7.68	7.76
T-β-naphthylamide	$C_{22}H_{22}O_4N_2S$	Light tufts	185°	4	S, 6.26	6.61
T-(1:3:4)-xylyl amide	$C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_2S$	Shining light tufts	139°	3	S, 7.32	7.21
D-di-n-propylamide	$C_{18}H_{34}O_4N_4S$	Short needles	123°	10	S, 8.06	7.95
D-di-isobutylamide	$C_{22}H_{42}O_4N_4S$	Light tufts	155°	12	S, 6.69	6.88
E-o-tolylamide sulphide	$C_{12}H_{13}O_3NS$	Small prisms	198°	6	S, 12.4	12.7
E-p-tolylamide sulphide	$C_{12}H_{13}O_3NS$	Hard needles	203°	6	S, 12.45	12.7
E-β-naphthylamide sulphide	$C_{18}H_{19}O_3NS$	Silky needles	208°	6	S, 11.01	11.14
E-1:3:4-xylylamate sulphide	$C_{14}H_{15}O_3NS$	Light tufts	175°	6	S, 11.79	12.08
E-1:4:5-xylylamate sulphide	$C_{14}H_{15}O_3NS$	Short crystals	187°	6	S, 11.88	12.08

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